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Improving road user perception in adverse weather: An augmented human–machine interface for remote assistants of automated vehicles

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ABSTRACT

Highly automated vehicles (SAE level 4) occasionally require human support. A remote assistant can help the vehicle from a distance. To date, virtually all human–machine interface (HMI) concepts for remote operation rely on cameras on board the vehicle for assessing its environment. However, in adverse weather, a remote assistant may not be able to decide based on video streams only. We propose an HMI concept for augmenting video streams with visualized data from vehicle sensors. In an experiment, 34 participants assisted the driving automation in a left-turn task using the augmented HMI concept. Visibility was varied by inducing fog. Results show that the augmented HMI effectively supported participants in their remote assistance task. Particularly when foggy, the augmentation reduced collisions, improved situation awareness, and received higher usability ratings. The results imply that augmentation is effective for increasing safety, especially in poor-visibility environments. Future research should examine implications for workplace design.

1. Introduction

Vehicle automation has considerable potential to improve safety, reliability, and passenger satisfaction as well as increase passenger capacity in public transport. Operating vehicles with a highly automated driving system (ADS, SAE level 4; [SAE International, 2021](#)) appears feasible in well controllable environments like highways. However, it is extremely challenging in less controllable environments like urban or mixed-traffic environments. The latter are characterized by a high degree of uncertainty and quick and dynamical changes ([Kalisvaart et al., 2021](#)). These characteristics are likely to result in situations that an ADS cannot resolve independently ([Kalisvaart, 2021](#)) and that may lead to deadlock situations in which the ADS cannot proceed.

In these situations, remote assistants (RAs) can help to find solutions particularly when ADS encounter unprecedented, rare, or complicated traffic situations. RAs ensure ADS functionality and provide guidance based on their experience and skills concerning the perception and processing of relevant information. Furthermore, RAs can respond to passenger requests and inform passengers about ongoing maneuvers, enhancing passenger satisfaction and building trust ([Brandt et al., 2023](#)). Therefore, remote operation contributes to ADS reliability and efficiency as situations transgressing the operational design domain of an ADS could be resolved more quickly ([Koopman & Wagner, 2017](#); [Schrank & Kettwich, 2021](#)). In addition, in some countries like Germany, remote operation is legally

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required for operating highly automated vehicles (SAE level 4) on public roads (StVG § 1e, 2021/12.07.2021).

In order for the remote operation system to work safely and effectively, special attention has to be allocated to the design of the interaction between the RA and the supervised vehicle. A central element of this human–machine interaction is the operator’s rapid and accurate perception of the traffic situation the vehicle is in. Interfaces for that interaction should support the RA in perceiving relevant road users to leverage the benefits of remote operation.

Remote operation of SAE level 4 automated vehicles can be conceptualized as remote driving and remote assistance (SAE International, 2021). In *remote driving*, sometimes referred to as direct or teleoperated driving, the RA executes the dynamic driving task including braking, steering, and accelerating in real time (SAE International, 2021). Thus, the RA’s tasks are similar to the ones that apply in in-vehicle driving. Indeed, the perception of the traffic situation and communication of steering and braking commands are mediated through an HMI. Event-based remote driving applies when a failure in the primary control system, such as the ADS, occurs (WG Research Needs in Teleoperation, 2024). In contrast, in *remote assistance*, operators support the ADS on a higher level, leaving the dynamic task to the ADS. Remote assistance is defined as “[...] event-driven provision, by a remotely located human, of information or advice to [a] vehicle in driverless operation in order to facilitate trip continuation when the ADS encounters a situation it cannot manage” (SAE International, 2021, p. 18).

In Germany, remote assistance is currently the sole legal implementation of vehicle remote operation on public roads (StVG § 1e, 2021/12.07.2021). Here, RAs are technical supervisors (“Technische Aufsicht”). They are responsible for checking and assisting HAVs upon vehicle request. Therefore, RAs get involved when an HAV detects an event that it cannot handle autonomously and thus submits a request for assistance to the RA. The RA’s workplace must optimally support the RAs task execution to support safe and efficient remote operation.

It is important to note that existing literature on remote operation generally revolves around remote driving. This implementation of remote operation has been considered from multiple perspectives. A vision on how to leverage the benefits of remote driving was outlined by T. Zhang (2020). Zhao, Nybacka, Aramrattana, et al. (2024) reviewed the technical aspects of remote driving including feedback, latency, and real-world applications. Meir et al. (2025) compiled the challenges of remote driving from a human factors perspective. While remote operation of HAVs faces general challenges regardless of the concrete implementation such as obtaining sufficient situation awareness (Mutzenich et al., 2021), remote assistance is a distinct approach. Remote assistance requires a specific investigation as the task of the operator differs significantly and is associated with distinct challenges (Vreeswijk et al., 2023). However, remote assistance has rarely been addressed by research to this date. This is particularly true for augmented and adaptive HMIs. No literature with these terms in conjunction with remote assistance was found in the existing body of literature. The present work aims to address this research gap.

In remote assistance, the RA oversees and supports the operation of one or multiple HAVs from a human–machine interface (HMI). Despite their relevance for remote assistance, suitable workplace HMIs have so far been covered poorly in the literature. Following a human-centered design process, Kettwich et al. (2021) designed and evaluated an HMI prototype for a remote operation workplace. The prototype was tailored to enable remote assistance of SAE level 4 shuttle buses from a public transport control center. Schrank, Walocha, et al. (2024) refined this HMI concept, built a prototypical workplace for remote assistance, and systematically evaluated it in an experiment with a dual-task paradigm. Some research in the area of remote operation addresses technical issues without focusing on human factors aspects (Amador et al., 2022; Andersson et al., 2024; Majstorovic et al., 2022; Zhao, Nybacka, Aramrattana, et al., 2024). Other research addressed software and hardware solutions for the remote operation of vehicles (e.g., DriveU.auto, 2023; Herger, 2023; T-Systems, 2023; Vay, 2022) but did not conduct systematic research in controlled laboratory environments to develop and evaluate a prototypical HMI for HAV remote assistance.

A concept relevant for HMI design is adaptivity. Adaptivity refers to a system change that is initiated by an external factor. Duley and Parasuraman (1999) defined adaptivity as *context sensitivity* implying that a system presents only the pieces of information to users that are relevant for the ongoing task. Knauss et al. (2018) also consider the user as a trigger of adaptation, e.g., for in-vehicle HMIs for driver assistance systems. As visualized in Fig. 1, two triggers of adaptivity in HMIs can be distinguished: Adaptation induced by (1) the

Fig. 1. Framework for adaptation in the automotive context by Knauss et al. (2018) and Diederichs et al. (2020). The HMI evaluated in this study is conceptualized for adaptation induced by context factors originating from the environment.

context (short-term), which splits up into (a) the user state, e.g., absent-minded, fatigued, or distracted, (b) the vehicle, e.g., sensor issues, and (c) the state of the environment, e.g., weather or road conditions, and (2) the *user* (long-term), i.e., personalization and personalized adaptation. The second trigger is based on user characteristics, traits, needs, conditions, preferences, and expectations.

In current remote operation workplace concepts, the video feed from cameras on board of the supervised HAV is a dominant source of information from the road environment. Therefore, information from the video feed has a considerable impact on the RA's performance and situation awareness. Video-based systems may work well under conditions with good visibility. However, in real-world operations, it is likely that suboptimal conditions prevail, for example regarding the visibility due to adverse weather conditions. When fog blocks the camera sensors, it may be highly challenging or even impossible for the RA to correctly assess a traffic situation. The blocked sensors may prevent the RA from identifying all relevant road users.

However, the set of HAV on-board sensors is usually not limited to video cameras. Many HAVs are equipped with radar, sonar, LiDAR, ultrasonic sensors, etc. (Sarker et al., 2020). Schrank, Wendorff, and Oehl (2024) proposed to utilize this sensor data as an additional source of information. Sensor data can be visualized in a way that makes it accessible to RAs. For example, in their online user study, the authors visualized LiDAR point clouds of real-world driving footage by applying object segmentation and classification algorithms. Subsequently, they color-coded the LiDAR points by object classes, e.g., highlighting all vulnerable road users in the same color, and laid the colored points over the video stream. In conditions with low video resolution, the authors found that particularly on the level of perceiving relevant road users, the color-coded LiDAR overlay led to an increase in objective situation awareness. This finding implies that overlaying visualized sensor data may at least partially compensate for a degraded video stream in terms of situation awareness.

The visibility of relevant objects is not only impeded by a degraded video stream. Low-light environments, e.g., at night, and adverse weather conditions, such as rain or fog, decrease object visibility considerably by distorting color, lowering contrast, blocking sensors, or simply lessening the quantity of available light which is required for an object to appear on a camera sensor (Y. Zhang et al., 2021). For instance, a literature review on the effect of adverse weather on HAVs found that operability of sensors is degraded in foggy and rainy conditions (Zang et al., 2019). Dannheim et al. (2014) showed that fog affects perception negatively by reducing image contrast and making pattern edge recognition more difficult. Impaired object perception may lead to dangerous situations. Thus, highly automated driving, which depends on video and sensor data for sensing and comprehending the traffic environment, may be severely impeded by adverse weather conditions and become more dangerous.

Consequently, the study reported in this paper visualizes additional sensor data to support peoples' perception of relevant objects. The data is visualized by highlighting road users with bounding boxes. Bounding boxes are two-dimensional rectangles or three-dimensional cuboids that specify the positions and type of objects, such as other vehicles, cyclists, and pedestrians. An example for bounding boxes is depicted in Fig. 2.

Bounding boxes facilitate the perception of elements in the environment by directing peoples' attention to stimuli and increasing the objects' salience, which supports level 1 of situation awareness (see section 1.5). Increasing salience makes it more likely that attention is directed to a stimulus whose salience is boosted (Wickens, 2015). This might be especially helpful when the induced cognitive load is high. Hence, by attaching visually salient bounding boxes to relevant road users, it is more likely that the RA directs their attention to them. However, augmenting all road users with bounding boxes may lead to visual clutter, especially in situations with many road users that are close to each other, bounding boxes may overlap, pile up or even obstruct other relevant objects. In these cases, bounding boxes may reduce the visibility of other relevant road users. Therefore, research has to find out which objects to highlight in a given situation to guide attention optimally.

An optimal allocation of attention could be achieved with *adaptive augmentation*. Here, only those road users will be augmented that are relevant for the current or upcoming interaction of the ego vehicle with surrounding road users. The relevance is operationalized by the likelihood for an interaction of the HAV and another road user in the respective scenario. Road users expected to interact with the

Fig. 2. Examples of bounding boxes surrounding road users. Copyright: DLR.

Fig. 3. Screenshots of left-turn scenarios from the simulation environment: (a) without fog, without augmentation, (b) without fog, with augmentation, (c) with fog, without augmentation, and (d) with fog, with augmentation.

HAV will be highlighted with boundary boxes. Thus, we balance the benefits of sensor data visualization while avoiding its downsides like visual cluttering, to improve an RA's attention allocation.

Based on the theoretical considerations, the research question of the present paper asks whether an augmented and adaptive HMI is better than a non-augmented and non-adaptive HMI in supporting remote assistants, particularly when cognitive load is increased. Effective support is characterized by a safe and timely intervention of the RA with moderate workload in a complex situation that cannot be resolved by the HAV independently but requires the remote assistant's attention and intervention. To answer that research question, we designed an experimental study. The experimental design and the hypotheses are described in detail in Section 2.6.

2. Methods

2.1. Sample

Participants were recruited through postings in the research institute's participant database. To take part, participants had to be between 20 and 55 years of age to avoid youth and age effects, be experienced drivers operationalized by having owned a driver's license for passenger cars for at least two years and steered a vehicle for at least 5000 km in the past twelve months. The participants took part voluntarily and were compensated for their participation with 25 euros. The Institutional Review Board of the research institution in which the study was conducted approved the study (decision no. 20/23). Informed consent was obtained from all participants before the experiment.

Of the $N = 37$ participants who took part in the study, three had to be excluded due to issues in the data collection process. Only participants with complete datasets ($N = 34$, nine female) were included in the analysis.

Participants' ages ranged from 20 to 48 years ($M = 28.03$, $SD = 7.72$). About one third of participants reported to drive every day (32.4 %), several times per week (35.3 %), or once per week or less (32.4 %). On average, participants reported to have driven 13,544 km ($SD = 7,831$) in the past twelve months. All of them had heard about AVs in the past. A majority of participants reported to be interested or strongly interested in AVs (76.5 %) indicated by responding with values 4 or 5 on a Likert scale on interest in AVs (1: "not interested at all" – 5: "very interested", $M = 4.09$, $SD = 0.83$). Twenty participants (58.8 %) stated to not have used AVs before. Participants reported medium to high affinity to technology (Franke et al., 2019; $M = 4.26$, $SD = 0.92$; 1 = low – 6 = high). Overall, participants stated a slightly positive attitude towards computer games (Chang et al., 2014; $M = 3.41$, $SD = 0.62$; 1 = "strongly disagree" – 5 = "strongly agree"). Nearly half of the participants stated to play video games once per month or less (44.1 %), about one quarter (23.5 %) reported to play video games several times per month or once per week. Thirty-two percent stated to play video games several times per week or daily. For video game genres, participants played adventure ($M = 3.06$, $SD = 1.69$; 1 = "less than once per month" – 6 = "every day"), and strategy games ($M = 2.12$, $SD = 1.43$) the most. Participants reported to only rarely commit different kinds of errors and violations while driving (Parker et al., 1995; $M = 1.80$, $SD = 0.38$; 1 = "never" – 6 = "nearly all the time"). Violations ($M = 2.22$, $SD = 0.77$) were reported to occur more often than lapses ($M = 1.90$, $SD = 0.38$) and errors ($M = 1.29$, $SD = 0.29$).

None of the participants reported to have experienced motion sickness throughout the study.

2.2. Setup

The following section describes the setup, including the primary and secondary tasks that participants were exposed to, as well as the experimental setup.

In the *primary task*, a driving scenario, a vehicle drove in highly automated mode for approximately two minutes at a speed of 50 km per hour. Then the HAV entered an intersection with a faulty traffic light leading to a minimal-risk state via stopping. The primary task of the RA was to be a fallback for the automated vehicle. In regular operations, the traffic light transmits its status automatically to approaching HAVs at a complex four-way intersection in an urban environment, enabling the vehicle to execute a left turn at the intersection without human involvement. In the present study, the automatic status transmission and the traffic lights were out of order (flashing yellow left turn arrow on the traffic light, Fig. 3a). Thus, the driving maneuver was a complex left turn as the ego-vehicle needed to yield to oncoming traffic before turning left. The operator's task was to determine when there is a gap in the stream of oncoming vehicles driving at a speed of 40 km per hour that is sufficient to turn left without causing a collision with the oncoming vehicles. The gaps were either 3 or 5 s long to distinguish between gaps that are rejected or accepted by a majority of individuals, respectively.

Once the operator identified a gap, they were asked to initiate the left-turn maneuver by pressing a button on a small keyboard. Subsequently, the HAV continued its ride by turning left. A trial ended after another phase of highly automated driving lasting for approx. 30 s.

Four versions of the left-turn scenario were used as primary tasks in the study. Fig. 3 displays screenshots of each version. They emerge from a fully crossed set of the 2×2 factors augmentation (yes/no) and fog (yes/no). As augmentation, three-dimensional bounding boxes around relevant road users derived from simulated sensor data were laid over the simulated video stream (Fig. 3b and d). For the foggy condition, a pretest was used to determine the ideal parameters regarding size and density of the foggy area to keep the detection of oncoming vehicles just above the perceptual threshold (Fig. 3c and d). This approach was taken to provide a realistic restriction of vision while avoiding bottom effects. The scenario versions were implemented and run live in the Unreal Engine (Epic Games, 2019) to enable a direct interaction of participants with the simulated vehicle.

The operators' *secondary task* was the n-back task (Kirchner, 1958). The task's goal was to induce and systematically manipulate cognitive load to simulate and modify the demands in cognitive processing capacities that may be posed to the operator in real

operations. Examples for high demands encompass the execution of particularly taxing remote assistance tasks or additional tasks, e.g., monitoring a voice channel. In this task, participants compare a presented digit with the digit presented n steps before the current one. The higher the n , the more digits have to be retained in the participants' working memory, increasing their workload. In this study, 1-back and 3-back were used. The n -back task was presented auditorily through a loudspeaker. Participants were instructed to give their responses verbally. The experimenter selected a list from a previously compiled set of five lists with digits ranging from one to nine. Starting in conjunction with the primary task, digits were presented sequentially every five seconds. The total number of n -back comparisons per trial depends on the duration of the trial, which is determined by the individual decision times to press the button. These ranged from approx. 15 to 35 s. Participants were instructed to respond verbally with "correct" if the digit presented n steps before the current one was identical with the current one, and to respond with "incorrect" if it was not. Participants were asked to respond before the next digit was presented, i.e., they had to respond within less than five seconds. The experimenter logged the participants' responses. The percentage of correct n -back comparisons was used as a measure for objective workload. It is defined as the ratio of correct n -back comparisons divided by all n -back comparisons in the respective trial. The lower the ratio is, the higher the measured mental workload.

Regarding the *experimental setup*, the participants sat in front of a wide-angle (32:9 ratio, 5120×1440 pixels resolution) 49" Dell monitor and a Stream Deck input pad (Fig. 4). Eye-tracking glasses (Pupil Labs, Pupil Core) and sensors to detect electrodermal activity (EDA; Shimmer Sensing, Shimmer3 GSR + Unit) and heart rate (ECG; Shimmer Sensing, Shimmer3 ECG Unit) were used to assess participants' glances and physiological responses.

2.3. Measures

In the present study, objective and subjective measures were used to investigate the participants' performance, situation awareness, mental workload, and usability.

2.3.1. Performance

Many indicators have been discussed as measures of RA performance like collision rate, distance to the closest vehicle, and decision time.

The number of collisions is a well-established indicator for the safety of road traffic (Aarts & van Schagen, 2006). Number of collisions can be related to the number of interactions in which a collision may occur. This ratio can be expressed as a percentage and reflects the collision rate. It can be compared to crash rate which is defined as the number of observed crashes divided by exposure, e.g., the distance travelled (Turner et al., 2018).

The spatial distance to the closest oncoming vehicle is another indicator for traffic safety and RA performance. It can be described as a "safety zone" around the vehicle (Wang et al., 2023). The larger the distance, the later a potential collision will happen and the more time drivers or RAs have to react.

In addition, the decision time measured from the standstill to the vehicle to the initiation of the driving maneuver is another indicator of traffic safety. Quante et al. (2021) analyzed real-world data on an urban intersection. They found 50 percent of drivers turned left within 4.7 s. Zgonnikov et al. (2022) created a cognitive model of left-turn decisions. Time gaps with a duration of 4, 5 and 6 s were specified as levels of the independent variable time-to-arrival. Drivers were more likely to accept an available gap the longer it was.

Fig. 4. Experimental setup.

In the present study, we collected four measures to quantify the participants' primary task performance based on the discussion above. First, we assessed *collision rate*. Collision rate is the percentage of trials in which the HAV hits an oncoming vehicle when turning left. It is a safety indicator; conditions with a lower collision rate are considered safer. Second, we assessed *distance* of the HAV to the closest oncoming vehicle when starting the left turn maneuver. More precisely, the measure captured the distance in meters between the front right corner of the HAV to the center of the closest oncoming vehicle's front at the moment when the ego vehicle enters the lane of the oncoming traffic. Third, *decision time* refers to the duration in seconds from the moment the HAV enters its minimum-risk state, i.e., full stop, until the participant presses the button to turn.

2.3.2. Situation awareness

Similar to a driver, a remote assistant (RA) needs to perceive and identify relevant elements of a traffic situation. They must integrate them to a coherent understanding of the situation and predict how relevant elements will change in the future. These tasks are related to situation awareness (SA). The hierarchical SA model of Endsley (1995) proposes three levels of SA. A higher level of correct SA can only be reached if the lower levels have been accomplished. On SA level 1, a RA must *perceive* characteristics of the traffic environment like road layout and condition, traffic signs, and other road users. To reach SA level 2, the RA analyzes and integrates these elements to "[...] form a holistic picture of the environment, *comprehending* the significance of objects and events." (Endsley, 1995, p. 37). For example, a pedestrian crossing an HAV's lane is relevant to the RA's goal to continuously drive on this lane. On SA level 3, the RA *predicts* how the situation will unfold. A result of high SA is that the RA may command the HAV to change lanes to avoid a possible collision with the pedestrian.

In a remote setting, it could be difficult to achieve high levels of SA because RAs cannot perceive the elements of the driving situation directly and without delay (SA level 1), or react immediately to them because of system delays (based on SA levels 2 and 3). By introducing bounding boxes, the RA's SA may be facilitated, which is another research question the current study aims to answer.

In the present study, we used the Situation Awareness Rating Technique (SART; Taylor, 1990) to assess the participants' situation awareness (SA). SART consists of the three subscales demand of attentional resources, supply of attentional resources, and understanding of the situation. Responses to each item were collected on a 7-point Likert scale. The pole descriptions depend on the specific item. For instance, the poles of the item "instability of the situation" were 1 = "The scenario is entirely stable" and 7 = "The scenario is entirely unstable". An overall SART score is calculated by deducting the difference of attentional demand and attentional supply from understanding.

2.3.3. Mental workload

Mental workload is the perceived difference between required and supplied information processing capability of people (Hart & Staveland, 1988). If the required information processing capacity exceeds the supplied capacity, mental workload is too high (overload) and people get stressed and their performance decreases. If the supplied capacity exceeds the required, people may get bored (underload) and their performance decreases as well. HMIs for remote operation should balance the requirements of tasks and people's capacity to avoid overload and underload (cf. Wickens, 1984).

In workplace design, all tasks need to be considered in workload assessment. Especially secondary tasks impose cognitive load on operators (Sweller, 1988), thereby increasing mental workload.

To examine the effect of secondary tasks on primary task performance, standardized tasks such as the n-back task (Kirchner, 1958) can be used. The n-back task has been used successfully to systematically vary cognitive load of vehicle operators (Pfanmüller et al., 2015; Reimer & Mehler, 2011; Wu et al., 2019).

In the present study, we measured both objective and subject mental workload. As a measure for objective mental workload, we recorded the percentage of correct n-back comparisons. For subjective mental workload, we administered the NASA Task Load Index (Hart & Staveland, 1988). It is an established multi-dimensional measure for participants to report how taxing they experienced a task. As suggested by Janczewski et al. (2022), the mental demand subscale was used to measure mental workload in an automotive context. Responses were collected on a 21-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = "low" to 21 = "high".

2.3.4. Usability

A system's usability is crucial for people's smooth interaction with it (Jordan, 2002). High subjective usability is achieved when the interaction between user and system is effective, efficient, and satisfying (ISO 9241-210:2019). Subjective usability determines how well system users can access information from the system and interact with it. While usability is limited to the interaction, user experience (UX) encompasses cognitive and emotional aspects related to an interaction also before and after the interaction takes place. In general, UX assesses how satisfied users are when interacting with a system (Minge et al., 2017; Hassenzahl, 2008). It is inevitable for developing successful user-centered products (Schrepp et al., 2017). Finally, user acceptance measures how eagerly users embrace a new system or technology. User acceptance is beneficial for the success of technology as it determines whether a new technology will be used by its designated user group (van der Laan, 1997). UX encompasses usability. All three concepts are relevant for designing the display component of an HMI for remote assistance as they influence efficient, effective, and safe operations.

In the present study, we applied the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ; Laugwitz et al., 2008) to measure usability. UEQ consists of a total of six subscales. The following three subscales were used to capture the construct usability: Perspicuity, Stimulation, and Novelty. Responses to each item were collected on a 7-point Likert scale. The pole descriptions are semantically opposed statements on each construct like 1 = "obstructive" to 7 = "supportive".

2.3.5. Sample indicators

Moreover, three questionnaires have been administered to participants as sample indicators to understand the composition of the participant group better.

ATI. The Affinity for Technology Interaction Scale (ATI; Franke et al., 2019) assesses the participants' affinity for technology. This construct entails a person's tendency to engage in interaction with technology. With its satisfying psychometric characteristics, the ATI scale measures the affinity for technology with nine items. Responses to each item were collected on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = "I completely disagree" to 6 = "I completely agree".

CGAS. The Computer Game Attitude Scale (Chang et al., 2014; CGAS) measures a user's attitude towards computer games. The instrument consists of 17 items clustered in the three subscales cognition, affection, and behavior. As the questionnaire only existed in an English version, the authors translated it to German.

DBQ. The Driver Behavior Questionnaire (DBQ) was developed by Reason et al. (1990) to predict the frequency of accidents from the quantity and quality of individual shortcomings in driving skills. The instrument distinguishes between lapses, errors, and violations. This study used a short version by Parker et al. (1995) which was translated to German by Glaser and Waschulewski (2005). Responses were collected on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = "never" to 6 = "very frequently".

2.4. Procedure

Initially, the experimenter briefed participants about the objectives of the study. Participants signed an informed consent, a non-disclosure agreement and a data protection declaration. Next, participants filled in the sociodemographic questionnaire and completed the ATI (Franke et al., 2019) and DBQ (Parker et al., 1995). Participants were instructed to imagine being a remote assistant who assists an HAV operating as a shuttle bus in public transport. Images of an exemplary HAV (German Aerospace Center [DLR], 2022) and of a comprehensive prototypical workstation for remote assistance (Schrank, Walocha, et al., 2024) were presented to participants. They were also informed about the setup and features of the RA's prototypical workplace for remote assistance. The experimenter invited participants to have a seat in front of their monitor. The experimenter described the scenario and the primary task to participants in detail. The participants completed a test trial in the condition without fog and augmentation to familiarize them with the task. In the next step, the cyan-colored bounding boxes and their purpose were introduced to the participants. In another test trial, participants experienced a situation with fog and with augmentation.

Subsequently, participants were familiarized with the secondary task, the n-back task. They were given an example for both variations of the task (1-back and 3-back) and familiarized themselves with the task until they felt confident with it. An optional short break of approximately five minutes concluded the training block.

After the break, EDA and EKG sensors were set up and participants were asked to wear eye-tracking glasses. Participants completed 12 experimental trials and 3 baseline trials with no n-back as well as 1-back and 3-back tasks. After each trial, participants filled in the NASA-TLX item and SART questionnaire. After the three baseline trials of the n-back task, solely NASA-TLX one-item measures were collected, no SART measures. Before carrying out the tasks, participants were reminded of their responsibility for the passengers' safety which demanded the operator's attention on the oncoming traffic at the intersection. Participants were instructed to prioritize the primary task but, at the same time, also complete the secondary task. Finally, participants filled in the usability scales of the UEQ questionnaire for each version of the left-turn scenario. A short debriefing completed the session. The whole procedure took about 1.5 to 2 h.

2.5. Experimental design and hypotheses

The study was conducted using a $3 \times 2 \times 2$ within-subject design with the independent variables (1) cognitive load (no secondary task, 1-back, 3-back task), (2) augmentation (with and without augmentation), and (3) visibility (with and without fog). Every participant completed all 12 conditions. The order of trials was counterbalanced across participants. This research question separates into four clusters of hypotheses (H1-4).

Regarding performance (H1), we hypothesize that conditions with augmentation will show an improved performance while conditions with fog and a higher cognitive load operationalized by a higher n in the n-back task will negatively affect performance. Furthermore, an interaction between augmentation and fog is expected: Conditions with fog will particularly benefit from the augmentation. Next, we expect situation awareness (H2) to be positively affected by augmentation and negatively affected by fog and higher cognitive load. We also consider an interaction between augmentation and fog. Regarding workload (H3), we assume that measured workload will be lower in the conditions with augmentation and higher in the conditions with fog as well as when cognitive load is higher. An interaction between augmentation and fog like in H1 is also expected here. Finally, usability (H4) is expected to be positively affected by augmentation and negatively by fog, with an interaction as previously described.

In summary, we expect augmentation to have a positive effect and fog to have a negative effect on the examined outcome variables, with an interaction effect of augmentation and fog underlining the particular helpfulness of the augmentation in conditions with fog.

3. Results

We applied repeated-measures analyses of variance (RM-ANOVA) to determine the influence of the experimental conditions augmentation, fog and n-back task on the dependent variables presented below.

3.1. Performance (H1)

3.1.1. Collision rate

Fig. 5 shows the effects of the independent variables on collision rate. Augmentation ($F(1, 33) = 43.44, p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.57$) and fog ($F(1, 33) = 27.12, p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.45$) had a significant main effect on collision rate. In addition, a significant interaction effect of augmentation and fog was observed ($F(1, 33) = 24.60, p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.43$). These findings are in line with H1.

3.1.2. Distance

Fig. 6 shows the effects of the independent variables on distance to the closest oncoming vehicle. Only fog ($F(1, 33) = 12.37, p < 0.01$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.27$) had a significant main effect on distance. A significant interaction effect of augmentation and fog was also observed ($F(1, 33) = 5.51, p = 0.025$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.14$). These findings are in line with H1, however, the main effect of augmentation on distance failed to reach significance ($F(1, 33) = 3.49, p = 0.071$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.10$).

3.1.3. Decision time

Fig. 7 shows the effects of the independent variables on decision time. Unlike predicted by H1, no significant main effect can be reported. The main effect of augmentation failed significance by a narrow margin ($F(1, 33) = 3.68, p = 0.064$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.10$). However, the interaction effect of augmentation and fog yielded significance ($F(1, 33) = 5.57, p = 0.024$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.14$). This finding is in line with H1.

3.2. Situation awareness (H2)

Fig. 8 shows the effects of the independent variables on situation awareness. All three of them yielded significant main effects: augmentation ($F(1, 33) = 71.66, p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.69$), fog ($F(1, 33) = 41.69, p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.56$), and n-back task ($F(2, 66) = 33.29, p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.50$). In addition, all two-way interactions reached the level of significance: augmentation and fog ($F(1, 33) = 38.61, p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.54$), fog and n-back ($F(1, 33) = 18.25, p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.36$), and, albeit weaker, augmentation and n-back ($F(2, 66) = 3.18, p = 0.048$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.54$). The three-way interaction was not significant ($F(2, 66) = 0.45, p = 0.642$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.01$). These findings are in line with H2.

3.3. Mental workload (H3)

3.3.1. Objective workload

Fig. 9 displays the effects of the independent variables on objective workload. The only significant main effect is n-back condition ($F(1, 33) = 161.10, p < 0.001$, partial $\eta^2 = 0.83$). Unlike assumed by H3, neither other main effects nor significant interactions were

Fig. 5. Means and error bars of collision rate (percentage of collision averaged across all trials) by n-back condition. Red line with squares: conditions without fog. Green line with circles: conditions with fog. Left panel: conditions without augmentation. Right panel: conditions with augmentation. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 6. Means and error bars of distance in meters of the ego-vehicle to the closest oncoming vehicle at the start of the left-turn maneuver by n-back condition. Red line with squares: conditions without fog. Green line with circles: conditions with fog. Left panel: conditions without augmentation. Right panel: conditions with augmentation. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 7. Means and error bars of decision time in seconds by n-back condition. Red line with squares: conditions without fog. Green line with circles: conditions with fog. Left panel: conditions without augmentation. Right panel: conditions with augmentation. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

observed.

3.3.2. Subjective workload

Regarding the subjective measure of workload, the line graph in Fig. 10 presents the results. In contrast to the objective workload measure reported above, all main effects (augmentation: $F(1, 33) = 19.52, p < 0.001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.37$; fog: $F(1, 33) = 27.14, p < 0.001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.45$; n-back: $F(2, 66) = 175.60, p < 0.001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.84$) and two interaction effects (augmentation \times fog: $F(1, 33) = 11.39, p < 0.01, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.26$; fog \times n-back: $F(2, 66) = 6.77, p < 0.01, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.17$) yielded significance. These results followed the assumptions of H3.

3.4. Usability (H4)

Fig. 11 shows the effects of the augmentation and fog on usability. Both independent variables were shown to have significant effects: augmentation ($F(1, 33) = 126.4, p < 0.001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.79$) and fog ($F(1, 33) = 144.1, p < 0.001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.81$). In addition, the interaction of both variables reached the level of significance: ($F(1, 33) = 128.5, p < 0.001, \text{partial } \eta^2 = 0.80$). These findings are in line with H4.

Fig. 8. Means and error bars of situation awareness (operationalized by SART score) by n-back condition. Red line with squares: conditions without fog. Green line with circles: conditions with fog. Left panel: conditions without augmentation. Right panel: conditions with augmentation. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 9. Means and error bars of objective workload (operationalized by percentage of correct n-back comparisons) by n-back condition. Red line with squares: conditions without fog. Green line with circles: conditions with fog. Left panel: conditions without augmentation. Right panel: conditions with augmentation. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

4. Discussion

The objective of this study was to present and evaluate an HMI concept that visualizes sensor data to support the situational assessment for remote assistants of highly automated vehicles (HAVs). We assessed operator performance, situation awareness (SA), mental workload, and usability. To our knowledge, it is the first experimental study that systematically investigated the interaction of visualized sensor data augmented onto a simulated video stream with poor visibility conditions and cognitive load.

In general, the results revealed that performance is lower in foggy driving conditions compared to those without fog. However, the augmented HMI concept highlighting relevant vehicles increased safety and performance, situation awareness, and usability especially in foggy situations, compensating for the negative impact of fog. Four clusters of hypotheses were postulated for the user study. They are discussed in the following sections.

4.1. Augmented HMI offsets negative effect of fog on performance

Regarding the three performance indicators, we observed significant interaction effects of augmentation and fog in all of them. The main effect of augmentation across the other conditions becomes evident only regarding collision rate. This finding indicates that there is a universal compensatory effect: The augmented HMI concept makes up for the loss of performance and the increase of accidents that the fog causes. While displaying augmented bounding boxes is universally beneficial only for reducing collision rate, not for distance or decision time, significant advantages of the augmentation show in all safety and performance variables when visibility is poor. These

Fig. 10. Means and error bars of subjective workload (operationalized by rating of NASA-TLX Mental Demand item) by n-back condition. Red line with squares: conditions without fog. Green line with circles: conditions with fog. Left panel: conditions without augmentation. Right panel: conditions with augmentation. (For interpretation of the references to color in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 11. Means and error bars of usability (operationalized by average of UEQ subscales Perspicuity, Stimulation, and Novelty) by fog condition. Left panel: conditions without augmentation. Right panel: conditions with augmentation.

results underline that using this augmentation can improve safety in low-visibility conditions, at least in the investigated use case of a complex left turn. This finding relates to a similar approach taken in the aviation domain: Fürstenau et al. (2009) and Fürstenau and Schmidt (2022) conceptualized a remote-control tower system for air traffic control (ATC). They incorporated an augmented vision video panorama and successfully tested it in low-visibility conditions to support perception of aircraft by remote ATC staff. In the automotive domain, our findings can be considered initial evidence for the viability of adaptive augmented HMIs for remote operation of HAVs. It is the first study in the context of road vehicle remote operation that not only presented an adaptive augmented HMI concept but also investigated it systematically in a user study. Future studies should examine the HMI concept in a holistic workplace setup and embed it into an adaptive system (c.f., Diederichs et al., 2020; Knauss et al., 2018).

For collision rate, we observed that in augmented conditions, the percentage of collisions was significantly lower than in conditions without augmentation. Since a lower collision rate is associated with increased traffic safety, it can be concluded that displaying augmentations improves safety of remote assistance. This finding can be linked to fundamental theories of perception and action. In direct perceptual theories, perceptual processes are assumed to first and foremost guide action and determine how individuals interact with their environment (Rogers, 2017). Therefore, the perception of the relevant elements in the traffic environment is a prerequisite for making a decision, i.e., to give clearance to the left-turn maneuver when the gap is sufficiently large, and not do so when a collision with oncoming vehicles would result from it. An accurate perception supports a valid decision. The role of the augmented HMI for remote assistants in safety can be paralleled to the role of advanced driver assistance systems (ADAS) for in-vehicle drivers. Schoner et al. (2024) analyzed crash data from the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration of the United States (NHTSA). They concluded that vehicles with ADAS were involved in head-on crashes and severe crashes overall less often than those without these

systems.

Another observed main effect was fog on collision rate and on distance: In scenarios with fog, the measured rate of collisions among all the trials was significantly higher, indicating that remote operation of HAV is less safe in situations with decreased visibility. Again, this result can also be explained by a link of perception and action. This finding is in line with other research that investigated the benefit of technologies in a poor-visibility environment. Van Nes et al. (2010) showed that an advanced in-vehicle system to homogenize driving speeds was not affected by foggy weather while a less advanced system worked less effective in a foggy environment. As another indicator of performance, distance to the closest oncoming vehicle, was significantly lower in the foggy conditions. This finding can be explained with a lower safety-margin due to limited visibility. It may also be interpreted as an indicator of riskier behavior as a shorter distance makes collisions more likely.

In conclusion, the uncovered *interaction* effect between augmentation and fog on collision rate, distance and decision time suggests that the potential benefit of the augmented HMI may be context-specific and granular. Similar findings are reported by research on ADAS: An empirical study found that the impact of ADAS depends on the contextual condition where they are deployed (Masello et al., 2022).

4.2. Augmented HMI improves situation awareness

Situation awareness (SA) was significantly affected by all investigated main effects and interaction effects. This result is in line with our hypothesis. It is an indicator that the augmentation did support the process of building and maintaining SA. As bounding boxes facilitate the recognition of dynamically moving objects that are relevant for the interaction, they improve SA at least on level 1, the perception of objects, according to Endsley's (1995) model. Whether the two successive levels, the integration of the elements to a coherent situation understanding (level 2) and projection how the situation will develop (level 3), benefit from the proposed augmented HMI remains to be investigated in further studies with methods than can distinguish between SA levels. This distinction could be made in a query-based paradigm with situation-specific items for each level of SA (c.f., Schrank, Wendorff, & Oehl, 2024).

Fog was found to have a detrimental effect on SA. This finding reflects the impairment of SA by a low-visibility condition: As the recognition of relevant objects in the situation is more difficult, it is harder to build SA. The subjectively perceived impairment of SA in low-visibility situations in this study is confirmed by objective measurements of SA in the literature. Lindemann et al. (2018) used an online freeze probe method to measure SA in a virtual reality user study in urban driving. They found a significant drop of SA scores in the foggy road environment compared to the clear weather condition.

In addition, the previously described interplay of augmentation and fog was also prevalent in SA, suggesting a particularly beneficial effect of our HMI concept in low-visibility conditions that compensates for degraded SA due to fog.

4.3. Augmented HMI reduces mental workload, particularly when foggy

Concerning mental workload, the results are twofold: While no significant effects of independent variables on *objective* workload were yielded except for the manipulation check, all main effects and two interaction effects presented themselves significant for *subjective* workload. In line with our hypotheses, subjective workload was indeed reduced by augmentation and increased by fog and a higher n-back conditions. This finding indicates that our augmented HMI concept showed effective in reducing participants' perceived workload. It also underscores the detrimental effect of poor visibility on workload, calling for support in perceiving relevant stimuli such as the proposed augmentation. This finding resonates with the significant impact of fog on mental workload in driving simulator research (Brookhuis et al., 2009). Importantly, the interaction effect between augmentation and fog also surfaced here, implying a positive effect of augmentation particularly in foggy situations. Lastly, the effect of n-back condition on subjective workload provides evidence for the successful induction of workload on the level of self-reports.

In order to explain the discrepancy between objective and subjective workload, it has to be noted that the subjective workload indicator considers a wider range of conditions. The subjective indicator collected data on all conditions, the objective indicator could not be measured in conditions without an n-back task since n-back comparisons could not be collected here. Also, participants might have allocated their working memory resources primarily to the primary task, leaving less resources for the secondary task. This shift of cognitive resources could explain the study's failure to find significant differences in objective workload.

4.4. Augmented HMI keeps usability at no-fog levels

In line with our expectations, both augmentation and fog as well as their interaction had a significant impact on usability. The compensatory effect of the augmentation found in the performance-based measures is resonated by the usability ratings: While the foggy conditions with augmentation are on par with the non-augmented conditions without fog regarding usability, ratings for foggy conditions without augmentation score significantly lower. The augmented view can therefore be considered to excel a camera-only view in its usability. Whether it improves usability at large when incorporated as an augmented HMI into the workspace for remote assistance is subject to future research.

In summary, the investigated augmented HMI concept proved significantly positive regarding performance, workload, situation awareness and usability, particularly in low-visibility conditions. These findings advocate for using augmented HMIs as part of an adaptive system for a remote assistance workplace.

4.5. Limitations

The study has at least three limitations. First, the experimental setup of the study in a laboratory environment leads to high internal validity. However, the external and ecological validity might be constrained. For example, the traffic scenario only included vehicles. Other road users like pedestrians and cyclists were excluded. For the sake of standardization and comparability across conditions, the traffic situation was identical except for the systematically manipulated independent variables presented before. In addition, it is up to future research to examine if and how the HMI concept is useful in other modes of precipitation or conditions of poor illumination, such as at night.

Second, only one specific scenario with a specific task and HMI concept was investigated in the study. While the results of the study provide initial evidence for the viability of augmented HMIs in the context of remote operation, their actual efficacy and usability heavily depends on the idiosyncratic design of the system including the deployed HMI. For instance, alternative implementations of the remote operation HMI to assess the traffic situation and to feed back the operator's input are conceivable. Their impact on performance and human factors outcome variables is supposed to be evaluated distinctly. The transferability of the specific task and the interaction design to a new use case needs to be critically evaluated for each system independently, as strong interdependencies amongst the system-relevant variables exist (Habibovic et al., 2020; Andersson et al., 2024).

Third, the composition of the sample could have influenced the results. The maximum age was limited to 55 years and had comparably ample driving experience. It is therefore questionable whether the results can be transferred to an older age group or less experienced individuals. However, the goals of this study were to emulate the performance of professionals who would execute this task on a regular base, having received extensive training before deployment. Thus, the sample was considered suitable to answer the posed research question.

Regarding situation awareness (SA), it has to be finally noted that this study collected data on the subjective component of SA only. A meta-analysis by Endsley (2020) has shown that objective and subjective indicators of SA tend to diverge. The subjective component is closely related to the extent of confidence of correctly understanding a situation (Endsley et al., 1998). Future research should also include objective measures of SA, such as freeze probe tasks (Salmon et al., 2009). Other measures of SA could also help elucidate the effective of augmentation on different levels of SA. For example, an augmentation could improve the detection of relevant users (SA level 1) but fail to support the operator in using this information to create a coherent understanding of a given situation (level 2) and to anticipate how the situation will unfold (level 3).

4.6. Conclusions and future research

This paper presented the experimental evaluation of an augmented HMI design for the workplace for remote assistance of highly automated vehicles (HAVs). Using a dual-task paradigm to manipulate cognitive load, participants interacted with a simulated HAV in a rather complex left-turn scenario. The results showed that the applied augmentation of the video feed by visualized sensor data supported the remote assistants in their task of supporting the HAV in assessing when the left turn can be conducted. The augmentation helped significantly reduce the number of collisions in a low-visibility, foggy, environment and yielded significantly higher ratings for situation awareness and usability while workload was rated significantly lower. These results provide initial evidence for the viability of HMIs with augmentation for remotely assisting HAVs. Transferred to an applied context, augmented HMIs as presented here could help to accelerate the introduction of HAVs on public roads. An augmented HMI makes it safer and more effective for remote assistants (RAs) to support the HAVs. As more use cases can be coped with thanks to the improved performance of the RAs, the downtime of the integrated system consisting of HAV and RA is decreased. Thus, in order to increase HAV system availability, it is advisable to equip the RA's workplace with an augmented HMI that improves the RA's detection rate of relevant objects including road users.

Future research could apply human-centered development and assessment of augmented HMI for HAV remote assistance by pursuing the following activities. First, it is advisable to incorporate objective measures for SA into the study design. Examples are freeze-probe tasks or eye tracking. These measures could disentangle different levels of SA and develop augmented HMIs that target these levels specifically.

Second, testing further use cases and scenarios in the same simulation environment could help ascertain the validity of an augmented HMI concept across use cases. An operational design domain (ODD) framework such as ASAM OpenODD (ASAM, 2021) could be used as a guide to ensure the systematic testing of the concept under all relevant circumstances.

Third, in addition to use cases, a method that systematically tests different tasks that a remote assistant (RA) is required to perform could be used to inform the development of augmented HMIs. An example for such a method is the Core Task Analysis, which has already been successfully conducted in the context of HAV remote operation (Koskinen et al., 2024).

Fourth, it could be worthwhile to investigate other approaches to augmented HMIs that support the RA in their task. For example, the HMI concept with bounding boxes used in this study could be transferred to other road users, e.g., pedestrians or cyclists. Additionally, HMI solutions that facilitate the understanding of the HAV's intention, e.g., what lane it intends to select or how to tackle a certain traffic situation.

Fifth, while the presented HMI concept is exclusively displayed on physical screens, exploring the potential of more immersive technologies, including virtual or augmented reality (VR/AR), could boost the feeling of telepresence (Minsky, 1980). Technologies to be investigated also include mixed reality approaches with chroma keying, head-mounted and head-up displays (Hosseini & Lienkamp, 2016). Using multimodal approaches that are not restricted to visual stimuli but also encompass auditory and force feedback (Zhao, Nybacka, Drugge, et al., 2024). While some research on remote driving exists that utilizes these technologies and modalities, literature regarding remote assistance remains scarce.

Sixth, augmented HMIs for remote assistance could also benefit from considering sources other than the environment to trigger the adaptive component. For example, the operator state could trigger adaptations in the event of operator fatigue or distraction as detected by operator state monitoring based on physiological data, eye tracking, and other sources (Walocha et al., 2024).

Finally, a comprehensive complication of research questions considering a plethora of aspects of remote operation can be found in an expert report issued by the German Federal Highway Research Institute BAST (WG Research Needs in Teleoperation, 2024). Researching these issues may contribute to boosting the deployment of safe and user-friendly systems of remote operation. Aramrattana et al. (2024) present a roadmap on how research remote assistance from major angles. Furthermore, Schrank, Merat, et al. (2024) describe key aspects for remote operation from a Human Factors perspective. Compatible with these considerations, augmented HMIs embedded in an adaptive framework have the potential to be a central component of remote operation.

Author contributions

All authors contributed to the study conception and design. Material preparation, data collection and analysis were performed by Andreas Schrank. The simulation environment was created by Marc Wilbrink. The first draft of the manuscript was written by Andreas Schrank and all authors commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Andreas Schrank: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Marc Wilbrink:** Software. **Stefan Brandenburg:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Investigation. **Michael Oehl:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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Glossary

ADAS: advanced driver assistance systems
 ADS: automated driving system
 HAV: highly automated vehicle
 HMI: human–machine interface
 RA: remote assistant
 RM-ANOVA: repeated-measures analysis of variance
 SA: situation awareness
 UX: user experience